

EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITE FIBRE BUNDLES TO IMPROVE THE TENSILE PERFORMANCE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the potential of Hierarchical Composite Fibre Bundles (HCFBs) to improve the tensile performance of UD composites by reducing stress concentrations near cluster of broken fibres. A Finite Element Model of a damaged HCFB was built by considering a hexagonal arrangement of sub-bundles with 16 to 128 fibres – modelled assuming axisymmetry – with the central one initially failed transversely to the load. An additional elastic or perfectly-plastic soft polymer is inserted in between sub-bundles, and its interface with the sub-bundles is modelled with cohesive zones. Under tensile load, two damage processes – interfacial damage and plasticity – are predicted. Both processes lead to a similar reduction of stress concentrations in the neighbouring of a broken sub-bundle, if equal shear strength is used in both cases. Results showed that: (i) a thin layer of soft polymer in between sub-bundles is enough to ensure translaminal crack deflection, thus minimizing stress concentrations at the vicinity of the crack without reducing the longitudinal stiffness/strength of the composite significantly, (ii) thinner sub-bundles lead to a shorter extent of interfacial damage with equivalent stress concentrations, and (iii) that it is necessary to control the interfacial shear strength at the surface of the sub-bundles to ensure the good balance between stress concentration and recovery length.

1 INTRODUCTION

The brittle behaviour of conventional UniDirectional (UD) Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) under tensile load in the fibre direction is widely reported in the literature. Experiments and modelling show that fibre damage in UD composites accumulates from very low applied loads, until it reaches a cluster size of approximately 16–32 broken fibres [1, 2], inducing such stress concentrations in neighbouring fibres that it leads to catastrophic failure. This research aims at understanding whether it is possible to promote a more gradual tensile failure process in a UD composite under tensile load, by organising the microstructure such that sub-critical clusters of broken fibres are isolated from one another to reduce stress concentrations in the material.

To isolate broken sub-critical clusters in UD composites, a bundle of fibres can be packed into sub-bundles to follow a hierarchical pattern, as already observed and studied in bio-materials (Figure 1a) [3]. Biomimetics suggests that the isolation of each sub-bundle can be achieved by inserting an interface (Figure 1b) or a soft polymer (Figure 1c) in between them. It is clear that the damage/plasticity mechanism

induced by the added interface/polymer in the vicinity of a translaminal sub-bundle crack (*i.e.* across fibres and matrix) reduces stress concentrations, which may provide an efficient isolation mechanism between adjacent sub-bundles.

Figure 1: (a) Plant vessel-bundle vascular system and the corresponding cross-section, composed of diverging vessel elements [3]; (b) HCFB, in which all sub-bundles are separated one from another by an interface (in yellow); (c) HCFB in which a soft interbundle polymer is introduced to separate the sub-bundles one from another. The sub-bundle/soft polymer interfaces are represented in yellow.

This work investigates the potential of Hierarchical Composite Fibre Bundles (HCFBs) to reduce stress concentrations in UD composites under longitudinal tensile load. The following objectives are addressed: (i) to predict the effect of the main mechanical and geometrical variables of HCFBs on their failure process, and (ii) to understand which mechanisms could reduce stress concentrations in HCFBs. For that, a Finite Element Model (FEM) is used to predict the stress distributions in the Neighbouring Sub-Bundles (NSBs) of a central failed sub-bundle (section 2). Results obtained with six selected sets of HCFBs configurations are presented (section 3) and analysed (section 4) to highlight the key parameters for promoting a more stable failure under tensile load.

2 FEM OF A PRE-FRACTURED HCFB

2.1 Geometry and mesh of the HCFB with one fractured sub-bundle

Figure 2a shows the considered HCFB geometry. A hierarchical unit cell is explicitly represented at the centre of the composite, composed by a Central Sub-Bundle (CSB) and 6 NSBs (following a hexagonal organisation), all embedded in an interbundle polymer. An external layer of Homogenized Composite (HC) surrounds the hierarchical unit cell. The entire geometry is defined by 5 parameters: (i) the fibre diameter ϕ^f , (ii) the number of fibres in each sub-bundle n_{SB}^f , (iii) the fibre volume fraction in each sub-bundle V_{SB}^f , (iv) the interbundle polymer volume fraction in the overall composite V_C^{IP} , and (v) the total number of fibres in the composite n_C^f .

Figures 2b and c show the geometry, mesh and boundary conditions of the considered FEM. Due to the symmetry along the z -axis, only one half of the HCFB is considered. Additionally, for simplicity, axisymmetry around the z -axis – following the fibre direction and passing at the centre of CSB – is assumed. Consequently, NSBs are modelled as a ring of CFRP, with a volume that is 6 times the volume of a sub-bundle and at a distance from the CSB equal to the smallest distance d^{hex} between two sub-bundles (Figure 2b). The interbundle polymer is modelled as two concentric rings, Interbundle Polymer 1 (IP1) – between CSB and NSBs, with a thickness equal to d^{hex} – and Interbundle Polymer 2 (IP2) – between NSBs and HC, with a thickness such that V_C^{IP} is verified within the hierarchical unit cell. A translaminal crack is introduced in CSB at $z = 0$, using symmetry and boundary conditions represented in Figure 2c. Two cohesive zones are introduced in the FEM at the interfaces of IP1 with CSB (CZ1) and NSBs (CZ2). For each HCFB configuration (defined in Section 2.4), convergence studies were performed

to verify that the mesh and the model's length (L) – which can change according to the configuration – led to converged stress distributions in NSBs. The element height h in IP1 is kept constant along the r -axis, and the element width increases linearly along the z -axis. It can be noted that the FEM can model the case of $V_C^{IP} = 0\%$, represented in Figure 1b (absence of interbundle polymer); in this case, IP1, IP2 and CZ2 are not represented.

Figure 2: (a) Idealised geometry of a pre-fractured HCFB ; (b) cross-section, (c) geometry and mesh of the corresponding pre-fractured axisymmetric FEM.

2.2 Mechanical properties

Sub-bundles – with the mechanical properties and fibre volume fraction of an AS4/3501-6 UD laminate as summarised in Table 1 – and homogenized composite – with mechanical properties and fibre volume fraction calculated using rule-of-mixture – were assumed elastic, with transverse isotropic constitutive behaviour. The reference interbundle polymer is Polyethersulfone (PES), with properties summarised in Table 1; two different constitutive laws were considered: isotropic elastic, and isotropic elastic-perfectly plastic. A bilinear traction-separation law was defined for both CZ1 and CZ2, with properties summarized in Table 2; mixed-mode was modelled with a linear interaction for both damage initiation and propagation.

2.3 Loading and computation

A uniform displacement was applied at $z = L$ such that the HCFB specimen was stretched along the fibre direction to a maximum overall strain of 2%. The model was implemented in the finite element code ABAQUS 6.13, and solved using an implicit and linear geometric formulation.

Sub-bundles					Interbundle polymer		
E_1 (GPa)	E_t (GPa)	G_{1t} (GPa)	ν_{1t}	V_{SB}^f (%)	E_{Int} (GPa)	ν_{Int}	σ_y (MPa)
126. [4]	11. [4]	6.6 [4]	0.28 [4]	60 [4]	2.45 [5]	0.31 [5]	107 ^(*)

(*) Provided by the manufacturer

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the sub-bundles (AS4/3501-6) and the interbundle polymer (PES). Longitudinal and transverse directions are indicated respectively by “l” and “t” in subscript. E and G are the tensile and shear elastic moduli respectively, ν is the Poisson’s ratio, and σ_y is the tensile yield strength of the interbundle polymer.

K_I (N/mm ³)	K_{II} (N/mm ³)	T_I (MPa)	G_{Ic} (kJ/mm ²)	G_{IIc} (kJ/mm ²)
$2 \cdot 10^6$ [6]	10^6 [6]	57 [7]	0.22 [4]	0.65 [4]

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the bilinear traction-separation cohesive law. K , T and G_c are the penalty stiffness, the strength, and the fracture toughness respectively, for pure mode-I and pure mode-II.

2.4 Parametric study

In order to study the influence of a broad range of geometries and properties on the stress concentrations in a HCFB, six sets of configurations were selected, as detailed in Table 3. For all sets, the number of fibres in the overall composite (n_C^f) is 25k. Within each set, four cases were investigated, each with $n_{SB}^f = 16, 32, 64$ or 128 fibres in each sub-bundle.

Set	Interbundle polymer		CZ1 and CZ2	Predicted mechanism at the central sub-bundle’s surface
	V_C^{IP}	Behaviour	T_{II}	
1	0%	–	$\sigma_y/\sqrt{3}$	interf. damage in CZ1
2	0%	–	$0.5 \cdot \sigma_y/\sqrt{3}$	long interf. damage in CZ1
3	15%	elastic	$\sigma_y/\sqrt{3}$	interf. damage in CZ1
4	15%	plastic	$2 \cdot \sigma_y/\sqrt{3}$	interf. plastic zone in IP1, CZ1 only damaged at the crack plane
5	50%	elastic	$\sigma_y/\sqrt{3}$	interf. damage in CZ1
6	50%	plastic	$2 \cdot \sigma_y/\sqrt{3}$	interf. plastic zone in IP1, CZ1 only damaged at the crack plane

Table 3: Specifications of sets used to study the influence of geometrical and material properties on the probability of unstable failure of a HCFB. For all sets, T_{II} is the shear strength of the interfaces CZ1 and CZ2.

3 RESULTS

For sets 1, 2, 3 and 5 (for which the shear strength of CZ1 and CZ2 is equal or below the shear yield stress of the interbundle polymer), a shear interfacial damage propagation is predicted in CZ1 (not in CZ2) during the tensile load (Figure 3). Although a high level of damage (over 0.95) is reached in CZ1 in the studied configurations, no element is totally failed at $\epsilon^\infty = 2\%$, which means that the proposed approach simulates cohesive fracture rather than brittle interfacial failure. A large plastic deformation zone propagating in IP1 along the CSB/IP1 interface in the first layer of finite elements is predicted for sets 4 and 6, for which the cohesive shear strength of CZ1 and CZ2 is above the shear yield stress of the interbundle polymer.

Figure 4 shows the stress distributions $\hat{\sigma}$ in NSBs (homogenized over the radial direction), predicted

for sets 1 to 6, with 16 (Figure 4a) and 128 (Figure 4b) fibres in each sub-bundle. The horizontal axis represents the distance z from the crack plane divided by the corresponding radius $R_{n_f}^{SB}$ of the sub-bundles, with n_{SB}^f fibres in each sub-bundle. The first intersection of each curve with the dashed-line (which indicates the value of the remote stress) corresponds to the recovery length of the associated HCFB configuration.

Figure 3: Shear-stress field σ_{zr} in CSB, NSBs, and IP1 (sets > 2), predicted by the FEM with $\epsilon^\infty = 1.5\%$, for sets 1, 5 and 6, with $n_{SB}^f = 16$ and 128 (the specimen's size changes with n_{SB}^f). Dashed white lines indicates the process zone of CZ1 (CZ2 is not damaged).

Figure 4: Tensile longitudinal stress distribution (homogenized over the radial direction) in NSBs predicted by the FEM with $\epsilon^\infty = 1.5\%$, for the sets described in Table 3, with (a) $n_{SB}^f = 16$, and (b) $n_{SB}^f = 128$. The horizontal axis represents the distance z from the crack plane divided by the corresponding radius $R_{n_f}^{SB}$ of the sub-bundles.

4 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 3 and 4 show that, for the same number of fibres within each sub-bundle, the longer the damaged/plastic zone at the broken sub-bundle's interface, the longer the recovery length in neighbouring sub-bundles. Then, the comparison between the different sets shows that:

- A the more fibres in each sub-bundle, the longer is the damaged/plastic zone at the broken sub-bundle's interface, and the more damaged is the interface in configurations with no plasticity in the interbundle polymer (sets 1, 2, 3 and 5). This leads to a longer recovery length in the cases with

more fibres in each sub-bundle. The stress concentration factor is almost unaffected by the number of fibres in each sub-bundle, and the stress distribution within the neighbouring sub-bundles also keeps a similar shape, as shown in Figure 4;

- B the lower the shear strength of the interface, or the lower the yield stress of the interbundle polymer, the longer is the interfacial damage/plastic zone at the broken sub-bundle's interface. Moreover, for two similar configurations, but one presenting damage at the broken sub-bundle's interface (*e.g.* set 3), and the other presenting a plastic zone near the broken sub-bundle's interface (*e.g.* set 4), the lengths of the two interfacial damaged/plastic zones are similar if the cohesive shear strength in the former is equal to the shear yield stress of the interbundle polymer in the latter. In this case, similar stress distributions are predicted in the neighbouring sub-bundles for low number of fibres in each sub-bundle, while a slightly longer recovery length and slightly reduced stress concentrations are predicted in configurations with no plasticity in the interbundle polymer (sets 1, 2, 3 and 5) for higher number of fibres within each sub-bundles (due to the higher damage level of the interface in this case as presented in previous point A);
- C the influence of the amount of interbundle polymer on the stress distribution in neighbouring sub-bundles is not significant.

Observations provided in the previous paragraph emphasize the influence of design and mechanical properties on the recovery length and stress concentrations in neighbouring sub-bundles. Therefore, they help to identify which parameters are crucial to provide a good isolation between sub-bundles, in order to reduce stress concentrations in the composite:

- first, observation A shows that the lower the number of fibres in each sub-bundle, the shorter the portion of the neighbouring sub-bundles that is subject to stress concentration. Therefore, the initial translaminal crack is less likely to propagate to the neighbouring sub-bundles, and a longer portion of the sub-bundles can fail independently of the first crack, both improving the multi-fragmentation potential of HCFBs;
- observation B establishes that damage/plasticity at the sub-bundles' interface reduces stress concentrations in the neighbouring sub-bundles, but increases the recovery length as well. In this case, further developments are required to assess which one must be promoted for a better isolation between sub-bundles;
- observation B also suggests that ensuring interfacial damage rather than plasticity in the interbundle polymer leads to slightly lower stress concentration for high number of fibres in each sub-bundles. However, the propagation of interfacial damage is more likely to be unstable than the propagation of interfacial plasticity, which indicates that interfacial plasticity should be promoted;
- observation C shows that the amount of interbundle polymer should be kept to a minimum, in order to preserve the stiffness of the composite while still reducing stress concentrations.

5 CONCLUSION

To promote the multi-fragmentation of HCFBs under tensile load, and therefore producing a more gradual tensile failure process in the material, the translaminal failure of a sub-bundle must not lead to the immediate failure of its neighbours. Following biomimetics, sub-bundles can be isolated by promoting crack deflection, therefore minimizing stress concentrations in the vicinity of a sub-bundle translaminal failure.

A FEM approach was proposed to investigate stress concentrations occurring in HCFBs in the vicinity of an initial translaminal crack in a sub-bundle. Several combinations of interfacial and mechanical

properties were defined, and the number of fibres in each sub-bundle varied from 16 to 128. The model demonstrated that the crack deflection ability induced by the hierarchical organisation is improved by keeping the sub-bundles with a small number of fibres. A second key point is that introducing a thin layer of soft and plastic polymer in between sub-bundles is enough to isolate broken sub-bundles and reduce stress concentrations, while preserving longitudinal stiffness and strength of usual UD laminates. The last point highlighted by the present work is the necessity to control the shear strength of the interface/interbundle polymer at the surface of the sub-bundles. A low value facilitates crack deflection, reducing stress concentrations in neighbouring sub-bundles by distributing them over a longer length. However, the longer this length, the more likely a weak zone of the neighbouring sub-bundles is to fail under stress concentrations, leading to a higher probability of translaminar crack propagation.

To understand whether low, high or intermediate values of interfacial shear strength are more effective in delaying failure, a statistical approach taking into account the strength distribution of the sub-bundles is required. The authors are currently improving a recently published approach [8] in order to use the complete stress distribution in the neighbouring sub-bundles under stress concentration obtained by the FEM, and this will be presented at the Conference.

The present work highlights the potential of HCFBs for improving the tensile performance of UD composites. With optimised design and mechanical properties, HCFBs will withstand larger clusters of broken fibres compared to UD laminates (which fail once a cluster of broken fibres reaches a critical size of 16–32 fibres), delaying catastrophic tensile failure and promoting multi-fragmentation of the composite. The potential of HCFBs remains to be experimentally investigated.

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